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WHO AND WHAT IS THEIR PEOPLE? HOW BRITISH POLITICAL LEADERS APPEALED TO THE PEOPLE DURING THE 2019 ELECTIONS

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The 2019 UK election was touted by many as a contest between the parliament and the people. But who were ‘the people’ in question? The rise of populist politics in recent years across the world had brought ‘the’ people squarely into political discussion and as a resource to be called on by populist politicians. Looking at twitter in the context of the UK election we can see what was meant in this context.

Table 1 shows some of the information about the use of Twitter by the five leaders during the electoral campaign^[1]. Among these, the number of tweets, and the percentage of those with the word ‘people,’ the hashtag use, the length of the tweet text, and the number of retweets. This last data allow us to understand if the tweets have resonated enough to encourage someone to share it with their followers. Data show that Corbyn is the most active leader with a higher percentage of tweets containing the word ‘people’ (15.1%), followed by Swinson (11.3%) and Johnson (10.4%).

Leader	Party	Tweets (N)	People tweets (%)	Hashtag (N)	Avg text (N)	Avg retweet (N)
Boris Johnson	Conservative	550	10.4	21	179	906
Jeremy Corbyn	Labour	756	15.1	30	214	4121
Jo Swinson	Liberal Democrats	203	11.3	22	198	742
Nicola Sturgeon	Scottish National	212	4.7	6	253	2456
Nigel Farage	Brexit	208	8.7	0	154	1985

Table 1 - 'People' in the leaders' tweets (from 12/10/2019 to 16/12/2019)

Figure 1 - Number of tweet (12 October - 16 December)

Figure 2 -Average number of retweet (12 October – 16 December

Table 2 shows the main issues covered by the leaders’ in their ‘people’ tweets. Among these, the Brexit topic occupies a prominent role. Swinson, for example, reached the highest value among all of the candidates (70.4%), covering the whole electoral campaign related to the opportunity to establish a second referendum to allow the ‘remainers’ another possibility.

@joswinson

Brexit will damage the livelihoods of people, families and communities across the whole United Kingdom.

Every vote for @LibDems is a vote to #StopBrexit. Together, we can build a #BrighterFuture. Join the fight to Stop Brexit now > libdems.org.uk/exit-brexit

1:03 PM · Nov 27, 2019

 1.5K people are Tweeting about this

Johnson used Brexit (26.4%) to talk mainly about the British priorities in his program: the NHS, security, and education/schools.

@BorisJohnson

The British people have had enough delay & uncertainty. I want us to #GetBrexitDone and spend next year focusing on the issues that matter - tackling violent crime, investing in our NHS & schools, and strengthening our economy.

2:34 PM · Nov 11, 2019

 2.1K people are Tweeting about this

While Corbyn was the candidate with the lowest percentage of ‘people’ tweets on Brexit

(6.8%), mainly focusing on Johnson's deal consequences.

Leader	Brexit	NHS	Security	School	Economy	Work policies	Improve UK
Boris Johnson	26.4	13.9	16.7	15.3	18.1	–	6.9
Jeremy Corbyn	6.8	12.2	2	–	12.3	6.8	14.3
Jo Swinson	70.4	–	–	–	–	–	–
Nicola Sturgeon	8.3	16.7	–	–	–	–	8.3 ^b
Nigel Farage	20	–	10	–	10	–	10

Table 2- Issues in the 'people tweets' (%)

Note: ^a campaign storytelling; ^b Improve Scotland.

The NHS issue is mainly a point of concern for Sturgeon (16.7%), the security one was an issue dealt with by the most right-wing candidates, while the economy was central between the two main challengers. The work issue was considered only by Corbyn (6.8%), as well as education by Johnson (15.3%). The generalist issue of 'how to improve own country', except for Swinson, was covered by all of the candidates, although for Sturgeon, it has always been

about how to improve Scotland.

Another interesting aspect was the issue of rights, namely concerning minorities, disabled, and women, which was the main issue for Sturgeon (50%) and one of the most important topics for Swinson (18.5%). Minor issues, related to the candidates' programs or strategy, were put in the "other" column. Among these, for example, Farage has repeatedly addressed the terrorism problem, Sturgeon Scotland's independence, and above all, Corbyn has much emphasized the storytelling of his electoral campaign, focusing on his militants and supporters.

'People' is today a neutral term, which only gains a specific connotation when it is properly contextualized. The adjective politicizes the noun by giving it a collective role or a particular identification. Thus, the 'people' can mean many different things to many various leaders in many different circumstances. Table 3 is an example of this.

Data show that an important percentage of the term 'people' is used generically without any specification by the five leaders, mainly by Farage (64.7%) and Corbyn (46.6%). This means that the people are considered to be one body, and they are often associated with a general interest.

@BorisJohnson

When people get up at the crack of dawn to prepare their family business, when people take out a mortgage to fund a new venture or risk everything on a new product or try to find a new market - we don't sneer at them. We cheer for them and ask how we can help.

11:03 AM · Nov 27, 2019

 5.5K people are Tweeting about this

@jeremycorbyn

The people telling you we can't solve the climate crisis helped create it.

The people telling you they won't sell off our NHS can afford private healthcare.

The people telling you we can't scrap tuition fees went to university for free.

They are not on your side.

1:38 PM · Dec 7, 2019

 26K people are Tweeting about this

For Johnson, the people also have a strong connotation as having British identification. This means that the 'British people' is in at least 36.8% of their tweets, which is an apparent reference to a large, circumscribed, and the defined universe.

'Young people' are the prerogative of female candidates, while the workers of men ones, especially in the economic area, for Johnson (22.8%). Corbyn, although he is the only candidate to speak directly about labour problems, rarely refers to workers as 'people' in his tweets (1.7%).

However, people are different things for each candidate; the people are amazing and passionate; the people are voters; the people are the weakest, including the sick and the

lowest of society; and the people are also ‘other peoples,’ which encompasses the Scots in Sturgeon’s storytelling or the militants and supporters in Corbyn’s tweets.

Leader	Generic / no specific	British	Young	Voters	Workers	Amazing	Weak	(
Boris Johnson	24.6	36.8	3.5	3.5	22.8	5.3	1.8	:
Jeremy Corbyn	46.6	0.9	3.4	6.9	1.7	1.7	9.5	:
Jo Swinson	26.9	–	11.5	46.2	–	–	7.7	:
Nicola Sturgeon	10	–	10	10	–	10	20	:
Nigel Farage	64.7	11.8	5.9	–	5.9	–	–	:

Table 3 – People’s adjectivation in the ‘people tweets’ (%)

Note: ^a e.g. members and supporters; ^b e.g. Scottish people.

To sum up, in these last months, the frontrunner Johnson had a single people to ‘love’, ‘look after’, ‘protect’, and from whom he asks for legitimacy throughout the election campaign. The runnerup Corbyn had more ‘peoples,’ building his whole campaign against someone, the few, to protect the many, continually calling on its militants and supporters to remain united.

Jeremy Corbyn
@jeremycorbyn

There are 150 billionaires in the UK while 14 million people live in poverty.

In a fair society there would be no billionaires and no one would live in poverty.

9:40 AM · Nov 1, 2019

 62.7K

 28.2K people are Tweeting about this

Thus while Corbyn looks toward his people Johnson institutionalizes himself having a direct relationship and paternalistic attitude in order to protect and represent the interests of his people.

Now what? The first will guide the UK towards the most critical change in recent years, and the second will face his people in the next crucial party congress, which will mark the end or continuity of his vision. Whatever their people have been, it will be interesting to understand what they will become in the coming months.

* This article reflects only the author's views and the European Commission or the Research Executive Agency is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained in such publicity. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no: European Union Grant Agreement number 838418.

[1] In this article are shown the first results of an analysis on this topic conducted during the 2019 UK electoral campaign from 12th October to 16th December on Twitter through the study of the use of the word 'people' by the foremost five political leaders.

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